

Trivalent Metal Chelates of Macrocycle derived from Dihydrazide and Aromatic Diketone

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Some trivalent metal chelates of macrocycle derived from carbohydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridine have been prepared. The chelates have been characterised by analysis, magnetic, conductance, electronic and infrared spectral studies.

Derivatives of 2,6-diacetylpyridine constitute an important class of chelating agents. Reports of some 3d transition metal complexes of 2,6-diacetylpyridine based hydrazones have been reported¹. The characterisation of divalent metal chelates of macrocycle derived from dihydrazide and aromatic diketone has been reported². Macrocylic metal chelates have been characterised recently³, but no reports are available of the macrocycles derived from dihydrazides and diketones. Thus, this article describes macrocylic chelates of macrocycle derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) show that metal chelates correspond to the formulae $[M(C_{20}H_{22}N_{10})X_3]$, where M = Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Mn^{III} or Co^{III}, and X = Cl, Br, NO₃ and NCS for Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} while X = CH₃COO for Mn^{III} and OH for Co^{III}. The values of molar conductance in DMF show that these complexes are uni-trivalent electrolytes. The tests for anions are positive, indicating their presence outside the coordination sphere. The molecular weights could not be determined since the complexes are insoluble in water.

Infrared spectra: A free amide group may coordinate through its oxygen or nitrogen. Since the infrared data indicate that the amide I, II and III bands shift to opposite directions, therefore, amide group neither coordinates through nitrogen or oxygen atoms of the macrocycle. On comparing the infrared spectra with hydrazones of

heterocyclic aldehydes, the bands at 1580–1640 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_{CN} modes. A strong band found at ~1630 cm⁻¹ with a shoulder at ~1610 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to symmetric and antisymmetric stretching modes of azomethyne linkage⁴. The appearance of ν_{CN} vibrations a lower range indicates the coordination of azomethyne group. This is further substantiated by the appearance of ν_{M-N} azomethine vibrations in the far infrared spectra.

The four $\nu_{C=C}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ pyridine skeletal frequencies at 1590–1610 (band I), 1560–1580 (band II), 1450–1490 (band III) and 1430–1440 cm⁻¹ (band IV) show changes in such a way that the pyridine nitrogen is coordinated to the metal atom⁵. Two strong bands are observed in the spectra of the pyridine based ligands at ~795 and 730 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{CN} and ϕ_{CN} modes respectively. The band ~730 cm⁻¹ splits into two components⁶ ~720 and 755 cm⁻¹. The C–C deformation mode increases in frequency from 400 to 415–435 cm⁻¹ and this change indicates pyridine nitrogen coordination⁷. The infrared spectra do not exhibit any spectral bands at 3200–3400 (NH₂) and ~1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O), thus indicating the absence of amino and carbonyl groups in the macrocycle in these chelates.

Therefore, the infrared spectra clearly indicate that the NH₂ groups of carbohydrazide have condensed with the carbonyl groups of 2,6-diacetylpyridine giving rise to 20-membered macrocycle containing 10 nitrogen atoms

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF TRIVALENT METAL CHELATES*

Compd.	Colour	Metal % :		Λ_M $\Omega^{-1}cm^{-2}mol^{-1}$
		Found	(Calcd.)	
[Cr(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)Cl ₃]	Green	8.50	(8.78)	210
[Cr(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)Br ₃]	Green	7.10	(7.16)	208
[Cr(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₃]	Green	7.50	(7.74)	—
[Cr(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NCS) ₃]	Green	7.80	(7.88)	—
[Fe(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀)Cl ₃]	Brown	9.20	(9.39)	224
[Fe(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)Br ₃]	Brown	7.58	(8.67)	—
[Fe(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₃]	Red	8.20	(8.28)	227
[Fe(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NCS) ₃]	Brown	8.40	(8.43)	—
[Mn(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(CH ₃ COO) ₃]	Red	8.15	(8.26)	225
[Co(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(OH) ₃]	Pink	16.50	(16.85)	216

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and X analysis.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Dq	Dt	DT	Dq	DT/DQ	μ_{eff} B.M.
$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_2)]\text{Cl}_3$	2110	451	6111	50791	0.12	3.68
$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_2)]\text{Br}_3$	2085	457	6192	50103	0.12	3.60
$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_2)](\text{NO}_3)_3$	2140	537	7276	50237	0.14	3.72
$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_2)](\text{NCS})_3$	2125	474	6422	50834	0.12	3.76
$[\text{Mn}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_2)](\text{OAc})_3$	1755	468	6341	40757	0.15	4.88
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_2)](\text{OH})_3$	2010	445	6030	48137	0.12	Diamag.

suitably placed for coordination. The ionic halides do not exert any detectable effect on infrared spectra while ionic nitrate and thiocyanate show characteristic bands at ~ 1350 , 1230 and 825 cm^{-1} , and ~ 2310 and 2110 cm^{-1} , respective of ionic nitrate and thiocyanate groups⁸. This contention is further supported by the absence of a bending mode at $\sim 470\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of thiocyanate group.

Magnetic and electronic spectral studies : The magnetic moments of Cr^{III} , Mn^{III} , Fe^{III} and Co^{III} complexes (3.60–3.70; 4.88, 5.76–5.84, B.M. respectively) are well within the range reported for octahedral complexes⁹. The diamagnetic nature of cobalt complex is usual as expected.

The electronic spectra of the chromium complexes exhibit bands at 16700 – 17150 (ν_1), 20850 – 21400 (ν_2), 25650 – 26150 (ν_3) and 29010 – 29400 cm^{-1} (ν_4) respectively. The spectra is consistent with six-coordinate octahedral geometry of the complexes. Assuming the effective symmetry to be D_{4h} , the bands may be assigned to ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_{g(a)}$, ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4B_{2g}$, ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_{g(b)}$ and ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ respectively. The first two bands are splits of ${}^4T_{1g}$ in quadrate fields^{10,11}.

The solution spectra of the manganese complex show bands at ~ 13450 , 17550 , 20800 and 35510 cm^{-1} , which are consistent with hexacoordinate octahedral environment around the metal atom. The first band ($\sim 13450\text{ cm}^{-1}$) assignable to ${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ is most convincing evidence for D_{4h} symmetry. The other bands may be assigned to ${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5B_{2g}$ and ${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ respectively. The higher energy band ($\sim 35510\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes may be assigned to π - π^* charge transfer due to azomethine linkage¹².

The solution spectra of the iron(III) complexes show well discernable absorption at 17500 – 18500 , 19800 and 24650 – 24950 cm^{-1} with another band in all the Fe^{III} complexes at $\sim 33575\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The lower energy bands (17500 – 19800 cm^{-1}) are probably due to splitting of ${}^4T_{1g}$ term and point towards the distorted nature of these complexes¹². The various bands may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (E) ($\sim 17500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ ($\sim 25000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) assuming the effective symmetry to be D_{4h} .

The electronic spectra of the cobalt(III) complex exhibit bands at ~ 16200 , 20100 , 25450 and 33570 cm^{-1} . The spectra is typical of pseudo-octahedral complexes of cobalt(III). Thus, various bands may be assigned as ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ respectively¹⁰, in increasing order of energy.

The values of various ligand field parameters Dq and

DT have been calculated using various energy level equations¹³. These classical parameters have been used to calculate Normalised Spherical Harmonic Hamiltonian parameters. The amount of distortion in the complexes has been calculated in terms of DT/DQ and the values of DT/DQ indicate a moderate distortion in these complexes.

Far-infrared spectra : The far-infrared spectra of all the complexes show absorption in the region 650 – 200 cm^{-1} . The bands observed at 490 – 500 (Cr-N), 350 – 370 (Mn-N), 400 – 415 (Fe-N) and 530 – 560 cm^{-1} (Co-N) vibration of azomethine group, are consistent with octahedral geometry around the metal atom¹⁴. The appearance of a band at $\sim 525\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the far-ir spectra of cobalt complex may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Co-O}}$ and indicate that OH group is coordinated in this complex¹⁵.

Hence, it is concluded that the amino groups of carbohydrazide are condensed with carbonyl groups of 2,6-diacetylpyridine to give rise a 20-membered ring metal macrocycles containing 10 nitrogen atoms. The macrocycle coordinates through four azomethyne nitrogens and two pyridine nitrogens giving rise to metal chelates of 20-membered macrocycle.

Experimental

A mixture of 2,6-diacetylpyridine (0.01 mol, 1.7 g) dissolved in methanol (50 ml) and methanolic solution of carbohydrazide (1.0 g, 0.01 mol) was stirred for 0.5 h. Then a methanolic solution (50 ml) of the metal salt (0.005 mol) was added to it followed by a few drops of glacial acetic acid and refluxed for 6 h on a water-bath. The mixture was concentrated to half its volume and set aside for 3 days. The crystals that separated was washed with acetone, ether, dried and crystallised from methanol, ($\sim 35\%$).

The complexes were found stable upto 200° , and insoluble in common solvents but soluble in DMF. The nitrate complexes were prepared from metal nitrates. Bromo and thiocyanate complexes were prepared by adding KBr and NH_4CNS to the solution of metal chlorides.

Magnetic moment measurement was carried out on a Princeton 155 magnetometer at 300 K. IR spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Backmann IR-12 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer. Conductance (in DMF) was measured by a Toshniwal CL-01 conductivity bridge. C, H and N analyses were done by microanalytical technique. Halides were determined by Vohlards method.

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